

SensEco: Fostering Creativity through Perspectives of Non-Human Species

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Human creativity exerts a growing, yet not always positive, influence on our planet, with unsustainable technologies contributing to pollution and the climate crisis. This research aims to cultivate a deeper ecological mindfulness among creators by fostering empathy with nonhuman stakeholders. How does a mole perceive the rumble of a passing train? What sensations accompany a bat navigating near human structures? Enter SensEco, an educational, turn-based, serious game designed to facilitate perspective-taking across diverse species. In this immersive experience, players inhabit a space outfitted with stimuli such as wind, sound, touch, smell, vibration, and light, enabling them to immerse themselves in different perspectives within the given environment. These sensations are tailored to mirror the perceptual realms of various species, termed agents. Through the lens of these agents, humanity appears as an uncontrollable and invasive force, often introducing obstacles rather than opportunities in the agent's habitat. Players encounter the tangible impact of human presence through mini-games, emulating the natural behaviors of these agents. Each turn of the game's overarching narrative reflects escalating human influence, making the mini-games increasingly difficult. Intended for daily play over several weeks, SensEco offers creators and designers an opportunity to deepen their comprehension of rapidly changing natural habitats shaped by human inventions and designs. By immersing themselves in the experiences of other life forms, players may develop a more eco-friendly creative mindset, preferring creative decisions that favor sustainable solutions - a shift to be quantified through mindset questionnaires and real-world creative performance tasks.

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